

**DYNAMICS AND MAIN DIRECTIONS OF SPIRITUAL AND CULTURAL
REFORMS IMPLEMENTED IN UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the issue of spiritual and cultural reforms in the development of New Uzbekistan, and it analyzes the achievements and reforms achieved in this field in our country. Also, the issue of spiritual and cultural reforms planned to be implemented in our country in the future was covered.

Key words: Culture, humanitarianism, geopolitical, values, civil society, patriotism.

**ДИНАМИКА И ОСНОВНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ДУХОВНЫХ И
КУЛЬТУРНЫХ РЕФОРМ, ОСУЩЕСТВЛЯЕМЫХ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ**

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена вопросу духовных и культурных реформ в развитии Нового Узбекистана, и в ней анализируются достижения и реформы, достигнутые в этой области в нашей стране. Также был затронут вопрос о духовных и культурных реформах, которые планируется осуществить в нашей стране в будущем.

Ключевые слова: культура, гуманизм, геополитика, ценности, гражданское общество, патриотизм.

Today, our country is making steady progress towards deepening democratic reforms and consistently continuing modernization processes. As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev specifically noted, "In the following years, we are working diligently to secure our national interests and to please our people, and we are achieving extremely important results. The most important result is the spiritual awakening of our society today, when the reforms we started have become irreversible. "No one can stop a spiritually awakened society, a nation that has set great tasks before itself and is confidently moving towards the future."

After all, it is extremely important to change people's hardened way of thinking, to get rid of the old way of thinking. He specifically noted that it is impossible to move forward in practice, especially to establish a new society, to introduce new relations.

Wide prospects of economic and social development, cultural and spiritual renewal have opened up for Uzbekistan, which has gained state independence. Thanks to the reforms implemented in our country, our society is moving towards an economic, spiritual and educational perspective. The development of spirituality and enlightenment is the most priority direction of state policy.

It should be noted that the dynamics of the spiritual and cultural reforms carried out in our country took place in the following 3 stages:

1. The stage of national-spiritual revival (until 1991-2000);
2. The stage of development of national-spiritual recovery (2001-2016);
3. The stage of national growth (from 2017 to the present).

Today's path of progress is manifested in the form of the human understanding of the world, its ability to use it for the sake of universal interests, and the democratic foundations of spiritual renewal of each nation serving the development of humanity.

The main goal of Uzbekistan's policy is to be able to stand firmly in the world economy, world politics, and world culture. In the renewal of society, special attention was paid in our country to preserving such values as the archons of spirituality - justice, honesty, equality, harmonious neighborliness and humanitarianism. They were given a new meaning, and all conditions and opportunities were created to achieve peace and democracy, prosperity, freedom of conscience, and the development of everyone in our country.

Because the times require continuous improvement of knowledge and skills of every person, including employees of internal affairs agencies, in order to meet today's requirements. If an employee has a wide range of knowledge, a developed worldview, and is worthy of the position he holds, he and others will find protection there. It was not for nothing that the great thinker Abu Rayhan Beruni said: "The essence of administration and management is to protect the rights of those who have suffered, to lose one's own peace for the sake of the peace of society."

Since August 31, 1991, when our country gained its national independence, it has been considered one of the most important issues to pay attention to spirituality and enlightenment. The following four criteria are used in the assessment of cultural heritage and in creating the conceptual basis of cultural policy in general:

- 1) humanitarianism;
- 2) development;
- 3) nationalism;
- 4) patriotism.

The priority directions for fundamental improvement of the system of spiritual and educational work should be defined as:

✓ to turn a healthy worldview and creativity into a nationwide movement in society by widely promoting the idea "From national recovery to national rise" based on the principle of goodness and humanity;

✓ ensuring continuity of spiritual education in family, educational organizations and neighborhoods;

✓ organization of activities in the direction of propaganda and education on a scientific basis, increasing the effectiveness of scientific and methodological research in the field, introducing a permanent monitoring system aimed at strengthening the stability of the social and spiritual environment;

✓ implementation of comprehensive measures aimed at eliminating vices such as indifference to the fate of the nation, localism, clan bias, corruption, disrespect for family values and irresponsibility for youth education;

✓ to increase the culture of using the Internet global information network of the population, to strengthen the ideological immunity against ideological and informational attacks;

✓ achieving the primacy of moral and ethical criteria, national and universal values in all types of culture, literature, cinema, theater, music and art, publishing and printing products, mass media;

✓ regular study of geopolitical and ideological processes, effective ideological struggle against terrorism, extremism, fanaticism, human trafficking, drug business and other dangerous threats, and development of international cooperation in this regard.

In the fourth year of independence, a serious event for the spiritual development of the country took place - on April 23, 1994, the Republican Public Center "Spirituality and Enlightenment" was established. The development history of the center can be divided into the following three stages:

the first stage (April 23, 1994 - September 3, 1999) - the period of formation of the Center;

the second stage (September 3, 1999 - August 25, 2006) - the period of achieving mutual coordination of spiritual-educational, ideological-ideological work through the Spirituality and Enlightenment Council;

the third stage (the period after August 25, 2006) is the period of promotion of the national idea and achievement of the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work.

the fourth stage (the period after July 28, 2017) - the period of increasing the efficiency of spiritual and educational work and raising the development of the field to a new level.

Now let's talk about the features of these four stages and the work done in these periods.

1. 1994-1999 were the formative years for the Center. Departments "Law and civil society", "Universal and national values", "Fund of ideas, opinions and programs", "Sociological studies" were created in the center, they were provided with mature personnel, and their work activities was put in .

On September 9, 1996, the decree of the President of the country on further improvement of the activity and efficiency of the "Spirituality and Enlightenment" public center was announced. In this document, attention was paid to spiritual and educational reforms at the level of state policy. Another important aspect of this document is that in order to educate the young generation to become owners of a bright future in the spirit of loyalty to our great traditions and high spiritual values.

Since 1997, October 1 has been declared the "Day of Teachers and Coaches".

In order to further revive the activity of the center, on July 24, 1998, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further deepen spiritual and educational reforms and increase its effectiveness" was announced. In it, there is insufficient attention to the importance of the work related to spirituality and enlightenment, and the involvement of local intellectuals, representatives of literature, art, and reputable activists in the wide promotion of the ideas of independence. it was noted that it is not being implemented consistently. It was noted that they do not coordinate their activities with "Nuroni", "Kamolot", "Mahalla", "Navroz", "Golden Heritage", "For a Healthy Generation" funds and creative associations.

2. The period of achieving mutual coordination of spiritual-educational, ideological-ideological works through the Spirituality and Enlightenment Council (September 3, 1999 - August 25, 2006). No matter how much the center strengthens its activities, the socio-political, economic, spiritual and educational reforms carried out in our country, the events happening around us, the processes of globalization in the world require raising the propaganda work to a new level. was doing Based on this need, state and non-state organizations with a number of goals

and tasks related to spiritual and educational promotion, in particular, "Marifatchilar", "Philosophers", "Historians" societies, "Health for the next generation", "Mahalla", "Kamalot", "Nuroni", "Navroz", "Golden heritage", media support funds, Republican "Spirituality and Enlightenment" Center, Writers, Composers, "Taviry Oyna" associations, Academy of Arts, Women's Committee, Academy of Sciences, Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, Ministry of Public Education, Culture and Sports Ministry of the Republic of Spirituality and Enlightenment

REFERENCES

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "Ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlar tizimini tubdan takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida" 26.03.2021 yildagi PQ-5040-son qarori, // <https://lex.uz/docs/-5344692>
2. Турдиев Б.С. Ўзбекистонда демократик жамият ривожланишида маънавий янгиланишлар стратегияси. Монография. –Т.: "Lesson Press" нашриёти, 2023. -Б.64.
3. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "Ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlar tizimini tubdan takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida" 26.03.2021 yildagi PQ-5040-son qarori, // <https://lex.uz/docs/-5344692>
4. Sadullayev, U. (2023). THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN NEIGHBORHOOD MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 132–135.
5. Shokir o'gli, U. S. (2023). MILLIY QADRIYATLARIMIZ ASROVCHISI. *Journal of new century innovations*, 35(1), 79-80.
6. Sadullayev, U. (2023). THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN NEIGHBORHOOD MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 132–135. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24060>
7. Bafoeva, R. (2023). INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK MAQOLLARINING SHAKLLANISH VA O'RGANILISH MASALALARI. *Научный Фокус*, 1(3), 29-31.
8. Bafoeva, R. (2023). INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK MAQOLLARINING KOGNITIV TAHLILI Ingliz va ozbek maqollari tizimlari haqida gap ketganda ularning mohiyati bir-biridan ajralib turishi aniq bo'ladi, chunki ular turli xil tarixiy, ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy sharoitlarda rivojlangan, va bu maqoll. *World of Science*, 6(6), 207-211.
9. Pirmanovna, N. G., & Bafoeva, R. (2023). LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK PROVERBS. *Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*, 11(4), 227-230.
10. Bafoeva, R. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERACTIVE GAMES IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES PROCESS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 510-512.
11. Toshpo'latova, S., & Ashurova, G. (2023). THE HISTORY AND DESCRIPTION OF THE WORK OF M. S. ANDREYEV - "ARK BUKHARI". *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 404–409. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24229>
12. OXUNJONOVICH, Q. Z. (2022). CHANGES OF LYULI IDENTITY. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(3), 74-83.

13. Корёгдиев, З. О. (2016). ACTIVITIES OF AMUDARYA FLOTILLA AT THE END OF THE NINETEENTH CENTURY-BEGINNING OF THE TWENTIETH CENTURY HISTORY (" TURKESTAN COLLECTION" MATERIALS). Ученый XXI века, (12 (25)), 20-22.
14. Mavlanova Mehnbonu Obid qizi, & Koryogdiyev Zufar Okhunjonovich. (2023). THE ROLE OF NATIONAL VALUES AND SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL WORKS IN THE EDUCATION OF THE YOUNG GENERATION. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 17, 81–84. Retrieved from <https://sjird.journalspark.org/index.php/sjird/article/view/753>
15. Okhunjonovich, K. Z. (2023). THE EDUCATIONAL VALUE OF NATIONAL CUSTOMS AND TRADITIONS IN THE ERA OF GLOBALIZATION. *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 18, 64-66.
16. Berdiyeva, S. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF ROLE PLAYING ACTIVITIES IN IMPROVING LEARNERS' LANGUAGE SKILLS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 75-78.
17. Utkirovna, B. S. (2023). Characteristics of the Works of Charles Dickens. *European Science Methodical Journal*, 1(3), 24-28.
18. Utkerovna, B. S. (2023). SHUM BOLA ASARINING TARJIMASIDA TARJIMON MAHORATI. *DENMARK" THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS IN MODERN SOCIETY"*, 14(1).
19. Berdiyeva, S. (2023, October). ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF TEACHING THROUGH ROLE-PLAYING ACTIVITIES. In *Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education* (Vol. 1, No. 19, pp. 88-92).
20. Sitara Utkerovna Berdiyeva. (2023). THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN GAME-BASED LEARNING AND GAMIFICATION [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10033388>
21. Berdiyeva, S. (2023). BENEFITS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES THROUGH ROLE-PLAYING ACTIVITIES. *MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH*, 2(10), 723–729. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10034991>
22. Okhunjonovich, K. Z. (2021). Self-Awareness of Gypsies: Traditionality and Modernity. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 2(7), 33-42.